

The Implementation of Sharia Principles in Sharia Banking in Developing Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in Southeast Sulawesi

Ahmad Hamid, Muhammad Syarief, Muh Natsir, Muh. Yani Balaka

Article Info	Abstract
Article History	<p><i>This research is qualitative research to implement the principles of sharia in Islamic banking in Southeast Sulawesi. And the influence of Islamic principles in Islamic banking on MSMEs in Southeast Sulawesi. The data used are primary data and secondary data. The results showed that Islamic banking in Southeast Sulawesi against MSMEs in Southeast Sulawesi is implemented through financing with sharia principles consisting of Mudharabah principles, is financing the MSME sector with a profit-sharing process between PT BNI Syariah Kendari branch and the MSMEs who are customers, Musyarakat principle, is the principle of financing that is carried out to become working partners where MSMEs are willing to become partners of PT BNI Syariah Kendari branch and funds all business activities to achieve the desired results, and Murabahah principle is financing carried out in the form of buying and selling goods between PT BNI Syariah Kendari branch and MSME. Meanwhile, the principles of ijarah and ijarawah iqtina have not been applied due to a lack of knowledge and experience and the absence of a work program that underlies the principle of leasing in Islamic banking, which PT BNI Syariah Kendari implements. Through Islamic banking in Southeast Sulawesi, MSMEs have developed from year to year by showing the number of MSMEs through the mudharabah principle reaching 669 units, MSMEs through community principles reaching 252 units, and MSME through the murabahah principle reaching 202 units. It also proves that PT BNI Syariah Kendari has implemented Islamic banking in Southeast Sulawesi. Constraints hindering the application of sharia banking to the MSME sector in Southeast Sulawesi Internal constraints include (a) Lack of employee knowledge of sharia principles, (b) Sharia banking work programs that still follow some conventional banking programs, (c) Lack of activities marketing of Islamic banking products in Southeast Sulawesi and external constraints include (a) Lack of understanding of MSMEs towards Islamic banking, (b) The lack of MSME sector that implements Islamic sharia, (c) The number of MSMEs does not have complete business aspects and (d) Lack of MSME assets which can be used as capital and goods for sale and purchase and (e) some MSMEs always experience losses.</i></p>
Received: April 09, 2021	
Accepted: June 07, 2021	
Keywords: Enterprises, Sharia Principles, customers	
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4906535	

Introduction

The application of the mudharabah principle in Islamic banks aims to increase the ability to earn profits (mudharib), where Islamic banks provide capital to carry out business activities carried out by their customers. In this principle, as the owner of capital (shahibul amal), the bank entrusts a certain amount of capital to the public (customers) who are considered productive. The application of the mudharabah principle may be limited to a specific period, and the cooperation contract must not be linked to past events, and there is no compensation in the mudharabah because it is a mandate (yad al amanah).

The application of the musyarakah principle is used in forming partnerships with a profit-sharing ratio under the agreement, while losses are borne proportionally according to the capital contribution. Musyarakah financing is a source of capital for business actors as working partners to obtain the benefits expected by capital owners, in this case, a Sharia bank. The principle of murabahah in Islamic banking can be used for consumptive purposes such as purchasing motorized vehicles, houses, and other household appliances, productive purposes such as working capital or investment needs. Bank provides Murabahah financing to the customer in the form of a

notarized or underhanded agreement between the bank and the customer. The principle of Ijarah, according to Sayyid Sabiq in Fiqh Sunnah, al ijarah comes from the word al-ajru (wages), which means al-iwadh (compensation), which is a contract of transfer of use rights from goods or services followed by payment of wages or rental fees without accompanied by the transfer of ownership rights such as safekeeping of certificates and certificates to obtain funds from a Sharia bank. In this principle, the bank guarantees the assets kept by the customer while using Islamic bank capital. Ijarah wa iqtina is one of the principles of financing capital goods accompanied by the transfer of ownership of leased goods from the bank to other parties. Financing with the principle of Ijarah wa iqtina does not guarantee the existence of goods to one party because the goods will be lent to the other party.

The nuances of religiosity in economic practice (Fauzan, 2010 in Inzani, 2015) Economic activities that involve many professionals while ignoring religious values are often seen as the trigger for the destruction of various life orders in society. Travis (2007) in Inzani (2015) researched the relationship between religion and entrepreneurship in America, finding how religiosity can increase entrepreneur productivity. The same thing is also found by David (2007) in Inzani (2015), which explains that religiosity values affect a person's decision to become entrepreneurial. According to Inzani (2015), micro-entrepreneurs with high religiosity are generally more prosperous than micro-entrepreneurs with low religiosity.

According to Syed Nawab Haider Naqvi (2009: 28), Islamic economics, in short, is a study of the economic behavior of representative Muslims in modern Muslim societies. According to Mohamed Aslam Mohamed Haneef Islam (2014: 90), a fact is that in conventional economics, religion is not related to economics. Religion only serves to provide strength in overcoming daily problems, a means to be friendly towards others, and as much as possible, religion should be separated from economic activities. In other words, religion does not regulate how an individual should carry out economic activities; religion is an individual's business with his God. The dichotomy between religion and human life, sacred and profane, between religion and other aspects of human life results from the secularization process practiced by Christians / Westerners, especially since the 17th century (Isnaini, 2015: 13).

Sharia banks are banks whose activities leave us with a problem of usury. Islamic banks or sharia banks operate without relying on interest (Muhammad, 2005: 13). Islamic banks or so-called interest-free banks are financial institutions or banks whose primary business is to provide credit and services in payment traffic and circulation of money whose operations are following the principles of Islamic shari'ah. Bank sharia has general functions include: M. Syafi'i Antonio (2001: 40)

1. Responsible for depositing customer funds
2. Manage investment from the funds obtained
3. Providers of financial transactions
4. Managers of zakat, infaq, and sadaqah

Islamic banking principles are made with rules and agreements between service providers and service users who enforce Islamic law in the process. Referring to www.syariahbank.com, the following are some principles implemented in Islamic banking:

1. Mudharabah, namely financing based on the principle of profit-sharing;
2. Musyarakah, namely financing based on equity participation;
3. Murabahah, namely the principle of buying and selling goods for a profit;
4. Ijarah, namely financing of capital goods based on the principle of a pure lease without choice; and
5. Ijarahwa Iqtina, namely financing with ownership of goods leased from the bank by our side..

Method

The type of research used in this research is case study research. The definition of case study research is a research method that specifically investigates contemporary phenomena (the object is ongoing or has taken place but still leaves a broad, solid, or specific impact and influence at the time the research was carried out) contained in a real-life context, using multiple data sources. In general, data is all facts and figures that can be used as material for compiling information. In qualitative research, data collection uses many interview techniques, so the data source is called informants. Informants are people who provide information related to the focus of the research. To make it easier to identify data sources, the researchers classified them into three, namely people, places, and symbols which were then shortened to 3P (person, place, paper). The source of the informant, researchers select reliable informants who must meet specific requirements according to the research problem, they are people whom the researcher thinks know a lot about the problem being studied, namely: the leadership of BNI Syariah regarding the implementation of Islamic banking, MSME business actors are always

customers of BNI Sharia. And employees of BNI Sharia customer service management. Data analysis is the process of systematically searching and compiling data obtained from interviews, field notes and documentation, and other materials collected and presented to others to increase understanding of these materials.

Results and Discussion

This research was conducted at PT. Bank BNI Syariah Kendari with the number of MSME customers as in the following table:

Table 5.5. MSME customers at PT. BNI Syariah Kendari

No	MSME Group	MSME Condition (Unit)					Total
		2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	
1	Micro	93	98	116	129	227	663
2	Small	52	60	71	72	76	331
3	Medium	8	15	41	44	45	153
	Total	153	173	228	245	348	1.147

Source: PT BNI Syariah Kendari (2021)

The data in the table above shows that PT. BNI Syariah Kendari Branch has served 1,147 MSME customers. In the business activities of each MSME, BNI Syariah provides financing based on customer demand, with 663 micro business units served, while 331 small businesses and 153 medium-sized businesses.

The following table presents the Application of Islamic banking for MSME customers at PT. Bank BNI Syariah Kendari branch.

Table 5.6. MSME customers at PT. Bank BNI Syariah Kendari Branch

No	Sharia Principle	MSME Service					Total
		2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	
1	<i>Mudharabah</i>	115	137	142	147	152	693
2	<i>Musyarakah</i>	53	50	48	51	50	252
3	<i>Murabahah</i>	35	39	43	45	40	202
4	<i>Ijarah</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-
5	<i>Ijarahwa Itiqna</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-

Source: PT BNI Syariah Kendari (2021)

Based on the data above, it can be explained that the implementation of Islamic banking has been carried out with sharia principles for the last 5 (five) years. The application of the *mudharabah* principle was carried out on 693 MSME units. The application of the *musyarakah* principle was carried out to be carried out on 252 MSME units, and the application of the *murabahah* principle was carried out on 202 MSME units. Meanwhile, it was found that the PT BNI Syariah Kendari branch had not implemented the principles of *ijarah* and *ijarah iqtna*.

Mudharaba Principles

The results showed that Islamic financing provisions are enforced or applied by Islamic banking in Indonesia for the MSME sector, including those carried out by PT. BNI Syariah Kendari branch in Southeast Sulawesi. It was confirmed by the Branch Manager of PT BNI Syariah Kendari in an interview that *mudharabah* financing is a form of mutually beneficial financing between the bank and the customer, so *mudharabah* financing has a profit-sharing principle.

According to the sharia, the interview shows that the *mudharaba* principle leads to the profit-sharing principle, which symbolizes justice between the owners of capital and workers. The terms of *mudharaba* financing applied to the MSME sector in Southeast Sulawesi are inseparable from the cooperation agreement between the two parties in which the first party (Malik, Shahib al-mal, PT. BNI Syariah Kendari branch) provides all the capital. In contrast, the second party (*'amil, mudharib*, the customer) acts as the manager, and the business's profits are divided among them according to the agreement outlined in the contract.

The proposed *mudharabah* agreement indicates an agreement between PT. BNI Syariah Kendari, in this case, Islamic banking with MSMEs as users of capital. The results of the study obtained data information about MSMEs that receive *mudharabah* financing as in the following table:

Table 5.7. MSME Users of Mudharabah Financing

No	Sharia Principle	MSME Service					Total
		2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	
1.	<i>Mudharabah</i>	115	137	142	147	152	693

Source: PT BNI Syariah Kendari (2021)

The results of an interview with the Chairman of PT BNI Syariah Kendari branch said that "usually business actors who use their capital run out of capital and close their businesses, besides that the investors charge high-interest money and cause business actors to be unable to return their working capital. Not smooth and failing business, but with the existence of *mudharabah* financing, business actors are invited to work together, and the results of work are shared as a given salary and fees.

Mudharabah financing has the main character based on the principle of profit-sharing and risk-sharing, where the profits are shared based on the agreement of the two parties, the ratio that has been previously agreed. Meanwhile, the funds' owner financial losses are borne by, while the manager does not compensate for the work.

Musharaka Principle

The *musyarakah* principle applied by Islamic banking places PT. BNI Syariah Kendari branch as a working partner. Data on the number of MSMEs that are partners of PT. BNI Syariah Kendari branch can be presented in the following table:

Table 5.8. MSME Users of *Musyarakah* Financing

No	Sharia Principle	MSME Service					Total
		2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	
1.	<i>Musyarakah</i>	53	50	48	51	50	252

Source: PT BNI Syariah Kendari (2021)

The table above shows that the number of MSMEs using *musharaka* financing in the last 5 (five) years, 2015-2019, was 252. Unlike the *mudharabah* principle, the community's principle has a reduced number of customers because not all MSMEs can become BNI Syariah partners. According to *muamalah* fiqh scholars, *musyarakah* is a contract of two or more parties who unite on the principle of capital or profit. (Sayid Sabiq).

The results showed that the provisions of the *Musyarakah* conditions must obey some *syirkah*, such as:

1. *Syirkah* Law

Syirkah is permissible. It is based on the arguments of the hadith of the Prophet Muhammad *Sallallahu 'alaihi wasallam* in the form of *taqdir* (provisions) against *syirkah*. When Allah sent the Majesty as a prophet, people at that time had prayed through *syirkah*, and Prophet Muhammad *Sallallahu 'alaihi wasallam* confirmed it. His words as narrated by Abu Hurairah ra: Allah '*Azza wa jalla* has said. The law of doing *syirkah* with an infidel Zimmi The law of doing *syirkah* with a zimmi infidel is also permissible. Imam Muslim once narrated from Abdullah ibn Umar who said: "The Messenger of Allah -peace, and prayer of Allah be upon him- ever employed the *khaibar* population (the Jewish population) by getting a share of the harvest of fruits and plants."

2. *Syirkah* Pillar

Contemporary scholars divide *Syirkah* into two: *syirkatul amlak* (ownership partner) and *syirkatul ukud* (agreement partner). *Syirkatul Ukud* is subdivided into several parts, including:

Syirkah Inan *Syirkah inan* is a *syirkah* in which two or more parties, each party donates capital and carries out work. An example for a *syirkah inan*: Khalid and Faizal share a burger business, and each spends IDR 50,000 per person. This partnership is allowed based on As-Sunnah and *ijma'sahabah*. It is required that the share capital is in the form of money. Capital in the form of assets such as carts must be accrued at the beginning of the transaction. This cooperation is built on the concept of representation (*wakalah*) and trust (*amanah*). By giving/sharing capital to their partner partners, each party means that they have given confidence and represented their partners to manage the business. Profits are based on all parties working together when the loss is based on capital allocation. In the book *Al-Jami'*, Abdur Razzak narrated from Ali r.a. who said: "losses depend on capital, while profits depend on what they agree on."

a. *Syirkah Abdan*

Syirkah abdan is a *syirkah* performed by two or more people, which only involves their workforce (body) without any capital partnership. For example, Jalal is a house builder, and Rafi is an electrician who works together to prepare a house project. Their partnership does not involve a boarding house. Profits are based

on their agreement. *Syirkah abdan* law is permissible based on the argument of As-sunnah. Ibn Mas'ud once said, "I shared with Ammar bin Yasir and Saad bin Abi Waqqash regarding the spoils of badr war. Sa'ad took two prisoners while Ammar and I did not bring anything" (Narrated by Abu Dawud and Atsram). Rasulullah s.a.w. knew this hadith, and he confirmed it.

- b. *Syirkah Mudharabah*
Syirkah Mudharabah is a *syirkah* of two or more parties provided that one party carries out work (charity) while the other party issues capital (mall). (An-Nabhani, 1990: 152). The term *mudharaba* is used by Iraqi scholars, while the Hijaz clerics call it *qiradh*. (Al-Jaziri, 1996: 42; Az-Zuhaili, 1984: 836). For example, Khairi, as an investor, gave his capital of RM100 thousand to Abu Abas, who acted as capital manager in the fish market.
- c. *Syirkah Wujud*
It is called *syirkah Wujud* because it is based on one's position, character, or expertise (*Wujud*) in society. *Syirkah Wujud* is a *syirkah* between 2 parties (for example, A and B) who are both doing work (charity), and a third party (for example C) that issues capital (mall). In this case, parties A and B are community leaders. It is essentially included in the *mudharabah syirkah* so that the provisions of the *mudharabah syirkah* apply to it. (An-Nabhani, 1990: 154)
- d. *Syirkah Mufawadhah*
Syirkah Mufawadhah is a *syirkah* between two or more parties that combines all of the above types of *syirkah* (*syirkah inan*, '*abdan*, *mudharabah* and *wujud*). *Syirkah Mufawadhah*, in this sense, according to An-Nabhani, is permissible. Because each type of *syirkah* that is valid is independent, it is also valid when combined with other types of *syirkah*. The profits obtained are divided based on agreement, while the losses are borne according to the type of *syirkah*; that is borne by the investor under the capital ratio (if in the form of *syirkah inan*) or borne by the equity investor (if it is in the form of *syirkah mudharabah*) or borne by the business entrepreneur based on the distribution of merchandise owned (if it is a *syirkah wujud*).
- e. *Syirkah Al Milk*
Syirkah Al Milk means co-ownership, which exists when two or more people acquire joint ownership or an asset. For example, two or more people receive an inheritance/grant/will to a piece of land or assets or a company, which can be divided or cannot be divided. In this case, the partners must share the assets and the income they can generate according to their respective portions until they decide to share or sell it. To maintain the continuity of the cooperation, all partners must approve decision-making concerning joint assets. In other words, a partner cannot act in the use of joint assets except with the permission of the partner concerned.

Murabaha Principles

BNI Syariah can meet the needs of the community with *murabahah* financing. The results of the study obtained data on the number of MSMEs that use *murabahah* principles.

Table 5.9. MSME Murabaha Financing Users

No	Sharia Principle	MSME Service					Total
		2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	
1.	<i>Murabahah</i>	35	39	43	45	40	202

Source: PT BNI Syariah Kendari (2021)

The table above shows that the number of MSMEs using *murabahah* financing in the last 5 (five) years, 2015-2019, was 202. The principle of Murabaha has a reduced number of customers because Bank BNI Syariah does not fulfill all MSMEs' needs. Sale and purchase agreements at Bank BNI Syariah are for the customers who meet the requirements under the applicable provisions. The results showed that the BNI Syariah bank served MSMEs that were feasible for financing through a buying and selling process. It was confirmed by the results of interviews with employees of Bank BNI Syariah Kendari branch, and he said that "*murabahah* financing is carried out to all customers and business actors who deserve such financing."

The interview results show that financing based on community principles places Bank BNI Syariah as the party that provides capital goods for sale to MSMEs in Southeast Sulawesi, and only 202 MSMEs use these sales products. It is evidence and the findings in this study that the *murabahah* principle has been applied but is only used by a small number of MSMEs in Southeast Sulawesi.

Ijarah Principles

In this study, *Ijarah* is an agreement to transfer the use of rights (benefits) of goods or services within a particular time with the payment of rent (*ujrah*), without being followed by the transfer of ownership goods

themselves. PT BNI Syariah Kendari branch has not obtained MSME customers who take advantage of financing with *ijarah* principles.

An interview with an employee of PT BNI Syariah Kendari branch said: "the principle of *ijarah* so far has not been applied in financing because no customer has requested this service. And PT BNI Syariah Kendari branch has also not thoroughly carried out *ijarah* financing because it has to consult with ulama entrusted to obtain information or *ijarah* rules." *Ijarah* rules can be changed according to the ulama's wishes, and ulama decisions must be followed to provide *ijarah* financing services.

The interview above shows that financing with the principle of *ijarah* is financing that is determined based on ulama decisions on goods that are eligible to become bank guarantees or are kept at PT BNI Syariah Kendari branch. However, when viewed from *fiqh*, an *ijarah* contract is a contract to rent people's services or rent property within a predetermined period and price. MSMEs are called *musta'jir*, while the PT BNI Syariah Kendari branch is called *ajir*. *Ijarah*, in the traditional context, does not make property change hands. The goods are stored at the PT BNI Syariah Kendari branch.

***Ijarawah Iqtina* Principle**

The application of the *Ijarawah Iqtina* principle (*ijarah muntahia bittamlik*) is related to the recognition of lease agreements for certain goods between the bank as the owner of the goods (*mu'ajjir*) and the customer as the lessee (*musta'jir*) for a while and at an agreed price. PT BNI Syariah Kendari branch has not implemented the principle of *ijarawah iqtina*, and the results of the research show that these sharia principles serve no customers or MSMEs.

Ijarawah Iqtina can be applied with sharia principles, including:

- (1) The promise of transferring property rights to the object of the contract in the fatwa of the National Sharia Council (DSN) Number 27/DSN-MUI/III/2002, which is not binding, contradicts the *syar'i* text and the principle of *Pacta Sun Servanda* as well as contradicting Fatwa DSN Number 85/DSN.-MUI/III/2012 concerning *wa'd* (promises) which oblige to fulfill promises.
- (2) Settlement of payment of *musta'jir wanprestasi* by charging all remaining *ujrah* until the end of the lease term in the Sharia Economic Law Compilation (KHES) or sharia banking practices is not following the law of *ijarah* and is not in line with the principle of benefit.
- (3) The review of *ujrah*, which only applied to the increase in *ujrah* and not applied to the reduction of *ujrah*, is contrary to the principle of balance (*tawazun*) and the principle of justice (*is*).

The development of MSMEs can be proven by the existence of good funding to show yield capability. In this study, the development of the MSME sector is seen from the number of MSMEs financed by PT BNI Syariah Kendari branch during the 2015-2019 period as in the following table:

Table 5.10. Development of MSMEs in the Application of Islamic Banking

No	Sharia Principle	MSME Service					Total
		2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	
1.	<i>Mudharabah</i>	115	137	142	147	152	693
2.	<i>Musyarakah</i>	53	50	48	51	50	252
3.	<i>Murabahah</i>	35	39	43	45	40	202
4.	<i>Ijarah</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-
5.	<i>Ijarahwa Itiqna</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-

Source: PT BNI Syariah Kendari (2021)

The data in the table above shows that the MSME sector's development in the 2015-2019 period after applying the *mudharabah* principle, the number of MSME sectors continued to grow until it reached 693 units. This development proves that the application of the *mudharabah* principle can improve the MSME sector. In applying the community principle, the number of MSMEs in the 2015-2019 period reached 252 units, and in applying the *murabahah* principle, the number of MSME sectors was 202 units. These results indicate that the application of Islamic banking in improving the MSME sector in Southeast Sulawesi.

The role of MSMEs is crucial for a country and has a vital role for a country's region. Southeast Sulawesi is one of the regions with the number of MSMEs reaching 72,109 units and spread across various sectors. The sectors developed in this research are yield capability, capital capacity, human resources, business feasibility, and institutional sectors.

What are the Constraints that Hinder the Implementation of Sharia Banking in the MSME Sector in Southeast Sulawesi?

Internal constraints

Internal constraints hinder the implementation of sharia banking activities in the MSME sector in Southeast Sulawesi, such as:

- a. Lack of employee knowledge of sharia principles,
- b. Sharia banking work program which still follows some conventional banking programs,
- c. Lack of marketing activities for Islamic banking products in Southeast Sulawesi.

External constraints

External constraints hinder the implementation of sharia banking activities in the MSME sector in Southeast Sulawesi, such as:

- a. Lack of MSME understanding of Islamic banking
- b. The lack of the MSME sector that implements Islamic sharia
- c. The number of MSMEs does not have complete business aspects
- d. Lack of MSME assets that can be used as capital and goods for sale and purchase.
- e. There are MSMEs that always experience losses

Solution

The application of Islamic banking is a great force for building Islamic sharia in business and banking. For this reason, the solutions that can be given to these constraints are as follows:

1. Solutions are provided to increase employees' knowledge of Islamic principles through education and job training programs for Islamic bank employees. This action is felt necessary to build employee knowledge in understanding and being familiar with Islamic banking products that must be applied in Islamic banking services in Southeast Sulawesi. The PT BNI Syariah Kendari branch provides education and training to employees at the PT Bank BNI Syariah Pusat Jakarta office.
2. Solutions are provided to build a sharia banking work program that can support the implementation of sharia banking in Southeast Sulawesi. The work program created includes a marketing program and Islamic banking products to no longer follow conventional banking programs.
3. Solutions are provided to add to the marketing activities of Islamic banking products in Southeast Sulawesi. They are opening a sharia banking marketing network with a network formed through MSMEs, which has become a customer of 1,147 units.
4. Lack of understanding of MSMEs towards sharia banking can be provided a solution through the socialization of Islamic banking to MSMEs in Southeast Sulawesi simultaneously with the substance of the activities focused on discussions related to the objectives and benefits of applying sharia principles to the MSME sector which so far have never received. Knowledge of sharia principles must be applied in business activities that are a blessing and bring good luck to MSME owners.
5. To maximize the MSME sector that implements Islamic sharia, it is necessary to implement sharia principles by the PT BNI Syariah Kendari branch. The application of sharia banking can be carried out through job training for MSMEs, and this activity is monitored and evaluated for its success rate so that the application of Islamic banking will have a positive impact on benefiting the MSME sector.
6. MSMEs do not have complete business aspects, supported by performance assistance to fulfill business aspects. The results showed that there are still many MSMEs that operate with permission from the urban village and pay retribution but do not have official and complete permits and are accompanied by institutional aspects so that MSMEs can develop properly.
7. MSME assets that can be used as capital and goods for sale and purchase. The solution is to manage MSME finances properly and be directed at the targets to be achieved.

Based on the research results stated above, it can be argued that the application of sharia banking can improve the MSME sector by overcoming the obstacles that hinder and follow sharia principles. Thus, the MSME sector can increase business activities based on sharia principles.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the research and wetting previously stated, it can be concluded as follows:

1. Sharia banking for MSMEs in Southeast Sulawesi is implemented in sharia principles financing. They consist of: (1) *Mudharabah* principles, namely financing with a profit-sharing process between PT BNI

- Syariah Kendari branch and MSMEs who are customers. (2) *Musyarakat*, namely the principle financing where MSMEs are willing to become PT BNI Syariah Kendari branch partners, funds all business activities to achieve the desired results. (3) *Murabahah*, namely financing made in buying and selling goods between PT BNI Syariah Kendari branch and MSMEs. Meanwhile, the principles of *ijarah* and *ijarawah iqtina* have not been applied due to a lack of knowledge and experience and the absence of a work program that underlies the principle of leasing in Islamic banking, which is implemented by PT BNI Syariah Kendari branch.
2. MSMEs through Islamic banking in Southeast Sulawesi have grown from year to year by showing the number of MSMEs through the *mudharabah* principle reaching 669 units, MSMEs through community principles reaching 252 units, and MSME through the *murabahah* principle reaching 202 units. It also proves that PT BNI Syariah Kendari branch has implemented Islamic banking in Southeast Sulawesi.
 3. Constraints that hinder the application of Islamic banking to the MSME sector in Southeast Sulawesi Internal constraints include (a) Lack of employee knowledge of sharia principles, (b) Sharia banking work programs that still follow some conventional banking programs, (c) Lack of marketing activities for Islamic banking products in Southeast Sulawesi and external constraints include (a) Lack of understanding of MSMEs towards Islamic banking, (b) Lack of MSME sector that implements Islamic sharia, (c) The number of MSMEs does not have complete business aspects and (d) Lack of MSME assets that can be used as capital and goods for sale and purchase and (e) some MSMEs always experience losses.

References

- Abdul Mufid, Agus Purwanto, Ahmad Asrof Fitri, Rohmad Adi Yulianto, Masduki Asbari, Fatrilia Rasyi Radita, Yoyok Cahyono. (2020). Indonesian Hijriah Calendar Unification Urgency in the Perspective of Maqasid Sunnah Nabawiyah and Maqasid Syariah : A Qualitative Literature Review. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, 29(04), 3095 -. Retrieved from <http://serisc.org/journals/index.php/IJAST/article/view/24139>
- Adiwarman Karim, 2002. *Ekonomi Mikro Islami* Jakarta: III T
- Ascarya, 2008. *Akad dan Produk Bank Syariah*, Jakarta: PT. Raja Grafindo Persada
- Djazuli A, dan Yadi Yanuari, 2001. *Lembaga-lembaga Perekonomian Umat (Sebuah Pengenalan)*, Jakarta: Rajawali Press.
- Hendri Hermawan Adinugraha, Ismail Fahmi Arrauf Nasution, Faisal FAISAL, Maraimbang Daulay, Ikhwanuddin Harahap, T. WILDAN, Muhamad Takhim, Agus Riyadi, Agus PURWANTO (2021). Halal Tourism in Indonesia: An Indonesian Council of Ulama National Sharia Board Fatwa Perspective. *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business* Vol 8 No 3 (2021) 0665–0673
- Hery Alamsyah, 2018. *Pembangunan Koperasi dan UMKM Provinsi Sulawesi Tenggara*. Yogyakarta; Rakornas Bidang Koperasi dan UMKM.
- Manan Muhammad Abdul, 1980. *Islamic Economics, Theory and Practice*, India: Idarah Adabiyah.
- Manan Muhammad Abdul, 1997. *Teori Dan Praktik Ekonomi Islam*, (Yogyakarta : PT. Dana Bhakti Wakaf.
- M. Syafi'i Antonio, 2001. *Bank Syari'ah: Dari Teori Ke Praktek*, Jakarta: Gema Insani Pers.
- Muhammad, 2004. *Manajemen Dana Bank Syariah*, Yogyakarta: Ekonisia UII.
- Muhammad, 2005. *Manajemen Bank Syari'ah*, Yogyakarta: UPP AMP YKPN
- Mustafa Edwin Nasution dkk, 2006. *Pengenalan Eksklusif Ekonomi Islam*, Jakarta: Kencana
- Peraturan Pemerintah No. 72 tahun 1992 tentang Bank Berdasarkan Prinsip Bagi Hasil.
- Pusat Pengkajian dan Pengembangan Ekonomi Islam (P3EI), 2011. *Ekonomi Islam*, Jakarta: PT Raja Grafindo Persada
- Putong Iskandar, 2010. *Economics :Pengantar Mikro dan Makro Edisi 4*. Jakarta: Mitra Wacana Media.
- Pusat Pengkajian dan Pengembangan Ekonomi Islam (P3EI), 2011. *Ekonomi Islam*, Jakarta: PT Raja Grafindo Persada.
- Sirojuzilam, 2008. *Ekonomi Pembangunan*, Yogyakarta : Andi Offset.
- Sugiyono, 2017. *Metode Penelitian*, Bandung, Alfabeta.
- Sukirno Sadono, 2007. *Teori Ekonomi*. Yogyakarta. BPF-UGM
- Syed Nawab Haider Naqvi, 2009. *Menggagas Ilmu Ekonomi Islam*, terj. M. Saiful Anam dan Muhammad Ufuqul Mubin, Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar.
- Tambunan, Tulus TH, 2009. *Globalisasi dan Perdagangan Internasional*, Bogor : Ghalia Indonesia.
- Undang-Undang Nomor 10 Tahun 1998 Tentang Perbankan
- Undang-Undang nomor 21 tahun 2008 Perbankan Syariah
- UU No. 7 tahun 1992 Tentang Perbankan.
- Novia Nengsih (2015). *Penerapan Perbankan Syariah Dalam Mengimplementasikan Financial Inclusion di Indonesia*. *Jurnal Univesitas Islam Negeri Syarif Hidayatullah Jakarta*.

- Ariani, 2017. Kajian strategi pengembangan Usaha mikro kecil dan menengah (UMKM) Di Kota Tarakan. Jurnal Organisasi dan Manajemen Fakultas Ekonomi Universitas Borneo Tarakan, Tarakan, Indonesia.
- Fauzan, 2013. Pengaruh Religiusitas Terhadap Etika Berbisnis (Studi pada RM. Padang di Kota Malang) Jurnal Manajemen Dan Kewirausahaan, Vol.15, No. 1, , hal. 53-64
- Isnaini Harapan, 2016. Penerapatan Perbankan Syariah Terhadap Sektor UMKM di Sumatera Utara. Sumatera Utara, Disertasi Universitas Islam Negeri Sumatera Utara.
- Lucky Nugroho (2018) Persepsi Pengusaha Umkm Terhadap Peran Bank Syariah. Jakarta . Jurnal Sikap. Universitas Mercubuana.
- Mohamed Aslam Mohamed Haneef. Islam, “The Islamic Worldview, and Islamic Economics. I IUM Journal of Economics & Management, No. 5
- Muslimin Kara, 2013. Pembiayaan Perbankan Syariah Terhadap Pengembangan Usaha Mikro, Kecil, Dan Menengah” Ahkam: Vol. XIII, No. 2, Juli 2013.
- Novia Nengsih, 2015. Peran perbankan syariah dalam mengimplementasikan Keuangan Inklusif di Indonesia. Jurnal Etikonomi UIN Syarif Hidayatullah Jakarta.
- Nurul Huda, 2010. Keterkaitan Perbankan Syariah dengan Usaha Mikro Kecil Menengah (UMKM) di Indonesia. Jurnal Ekonomi Fakultas Ekonomi Universitas Yarsi
- PURWANTO, A., Ardiyanto, J., & Sudargini, Y. (2021). Intention Factors of Halal Food Purchase among Student Consumers: An Explanatory Sequential Mixed Methods Study. *Journal of Industrial Engineering & Management Research*, 2(2), 21 - 34. <https://doi.org/10.7777/jiemar.v2i2.124>
- Prihatin Lumbanraja, 2017. Pengembangan Usaha Mikro Kecil Dan Menengah (UMKM) Kerajinan Menjahit Dan Bordir Di Kecamatan Medan Area Kota Medan <http://jurnal.usu.ac.id/abdimas>
- Yuli Rahmini Suci, 2017. Perkembangan umkm (Usaha Mikro Kecil dan Menengah) di Indonesia Jurnal Ekonomi. Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi Balikpapan email: yulirahmini@ymail.com..

Author Information

Ahmad Hamid

Students of Doctoral Program in Economics,
University of Halu Oleo Kendari

Muhammad Syarief

Lecturer at the Faculty of Economics and Business,
University of Halu Oleo Kendari
Kampus Hijau Bumi Tridharma, Anduonohu, Kec. Kambu,
Kota Kendari, Sulawesi Tenggara 93232

Muh Natsir

Lecturer at the Faculty of Economics and Business,
University of Halu Oleo Kendari
Kampus Hijau Bumi Tridharma, Anduonohu, Kec. Kambu,
Kota Kendari, Sulawesi Tenggara 93232

Muh. Yani Balaka

Lecturer at the Faculty of Economics and Business,
University of Halu Oleo Kendari
Kampus Hijau Bumi Tridharma, Anduonohu, Kec. Kambu,
Kota Kendari, Sulawesi Tenggara 93232
